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Abstract

Several articles in this issue of Health Psychology offer novel takes on familiar topics, such as the impact of moderation and mediation on people propensities to adopt healthy food and exercise routines. The purpose of this study is to choose a research topic that will pique the interest of linguists around the world. These linguists will then conduct empirical investigations on the under-researched areas, speeding up the development of this field.

Keywords

Health Psychology, education, linguists

1. Introduction

The fields of education and educational psychology have made major advances to our knowledge of the multiplicity of complex factors that come together to influence student educational experiences. These endeavors are based on tracing the evolution, causes, and outcomes of foundational transformation processes that boost learning and accomplishment. In an effort to accomplish this, researchers have resorted to novel quantitative methods. These methods are an attempt to rectify the shortcomings of earlier statistical procedures. Yet this isn't the only new thing happening. Though scholars now have access to a wider array of resources, further progress in the field of education is still necessary.

The recent methodological advancements that may help researchers work around these constraints. Modern research techniques, when applied to the field of education, open up a number of fascinating new avenues that have the potential to deepen our understanding of the subject at hand. For instance, they may shed light on the dynamic between shifts in core constructs used in research on what drives people to take action, such as success expectations, value assessments, and cost estimates. If we knew with a particular degree of certainty that a program would be completed successfully in one year, for instance, we might use LCSM to determine whether or not that degree of certainty was correlated with the program utility and intrinsic value, but not its cost.

Keeping with the same example, if we use mixture modeling instead of LCSM alone, we can see if the hypothesis that some subsets of students have nonlinearly decreasing. A deeper understanding of the dynamics of multidimensional change can be gained through an examination of the mediation processes that occur across time. This is because, theoretically speaking, studying these procedures has both immediate and downstream consequences [1]-[3].

Researchers in more theoretical domains can now examine their most pressing difficulties from a wider range of perspectives than ever before, all because to the rapid pace and wide range of improvements made to quantitative research tools. To better understand how student learning and motivation are influenced by the researchers may analyze the ways in which student peer networks influence their learning and motivation. Recent developments, such as user-friendly estimating subroutines and other advancements, in Bayesian modeling present an intriguing chance to investigate the rich information embedded in the data intricate structure. This is due to the fact that researchers now have access to more recent advancements in other significant quantitative fields, allowing for these adjustments to be made. Finally, researchers interested in causal processes and their impacts in settings where randomized control trials would be impractical might find study into quasiexperimental designs useful [4] [5].

The field of quantitative techniques, like many others, is constantly growing, both in terms of existing methods and brand-new ones being invented. However, one must make a choice between spending time staying on the cutting edge of one substantive domain and honing one quantitative skills. The goal of this supplemental issue of Educational Psychologist was to update readers on recent advances in quantitative approaches. Eight essays are featured in this volume, all of which aim to be both methodologically and didactically useful in helping applied

researchers see the potential for broadening their own study areas. Numerous themes, both conceptual and analytical, are discussed in depth throughout the pieces. What follows are brief summaries of the article descriptions. We are confident and source of motivation for our peers as they seek to expand the boundaries of education and educational psychology.

2. Literature Survey

The [5] introduce the reader to a novel method with the potential to greatly advance research in the fields of educational psychology and education. In particular, the authors discuss the topic of structuring trials with intended missing data, which can reduce data collection expenses and participant fatigue and burden without dramatically reducing statistical power. Key planned missing data designs, such as the multiform design, the longitudinal wave-missing design, and the two-method measurement design, are covered in this article. Various research scenarios can be accommodated by combining or expanding any of these planned missing data approaches. This page gives the material in sufficient detail while yet being accessible, allowing a large audience to grasp its meaning and appreciate the design potential for use in practical research. By following the above links, you will be able to access helpful resources.

The authors [6] write on data clustering, a feature of research designs that is used often in the field of education, in their article for this issue. They provide strong evidence against the standard practice in the social and behavioral sciences of using a blanket multilevel modeling strategy wherever nested data is present in an investigation. The optimum use of one time and energy can be achieved by selecting the latter option. This article equips its readers with the knowledge they need to conduct in-depth analyses of complex data. To achieve this goal, it describes the underlying assumptions of each framework and provides several illustrations of the types of research problems that can be addressed effectively within each framework. Good analytical decisions may be made in the face of complex facts, and this article equips readers with the necessary background to do so.

The authors [7] delves into a facet of mediation modeling that has been largely overlooked despite being crucial to the field in this issue of the journal. This article shows how researchers can benefit from using correctly constructed longitudinal mediation models to better explain interactions between variables or constructs of interest. Two other kinds of full mediation models are also included. This contribution aim is to interest readers in this timely subject by summarizing such cases. The presented examples aid in not just understanding but also

expanding upon the underlying principles. The strengths of this article lie in its concrete examples and explanations of why researchers might benefit from utilizing these types of analyses in their substantive work, as well as its valuable information for researchers.

The LCSM modeling framework is a 2016 contribution to this problem by the authors [8]. This framework was developed specifically for this problem, and it can be applied to the analysis of both univariate and multivariate transformations. Traditional mechanism, are shown to be special examples of the LCSM framework, and the authors provide persuasive evidence in support of this claim. According to Grimm and his coworkers, LCSM adaptability makes it possible to integrate studies of change processes with appropriate methods of analysis. This article serves as an excellent primer on LCSM, covering the basic concepts upon which the theory rests, as well as the equations that define the many key models and the proper way to interpret the values of their parameters. Article worked example does a great job of showing how LCSM may be used in practice. Researchers in the domains of education and educational psychology should benefit from this since it will allow them to (a) recognize LCSM usefulness and (b) successfully implement this analytical framework into their own work.

The authors [9] conducting cross-sectional research, latent profile analysis can be useful, but growth mixture modeling is more appropriate when conducting longitudinal studies. Both methods can be used to classify cases and data according to criteria of interest that were not apparent at first. Studies that aim to reveal elusive patterns of linkage and/or change can benefit greatly from the application. Accordingly, research aiming to reveal such patterns can benefit from the use of these instruments. Both the specific methods and the fundamentals shared by all mixture models are covered in detail in this article. The author examples, both of which are grounded in real data and show crucial issues, serve as a useful reminder to keep these factors in mind when applying these approaches to more in-depth study. This contribution exemplifies how, when properly applied, latent profile analysis and growth mixture modeling may significantly advance academic research and theory development.

The authors [10] places special emphasis on a category of modeling tools that have not been widely used in education research but are computationally realistic and easy to use. As the author points out, however, these challenges have been mostly overcome, and she feels that now is the time of academics working in the fields of education and educational psychology. The essay begins with an accessible explanation of Bayesian inference, then proceeds on to provide a conceptual introduction to several, fully fleshed-out examples. Diagnostic evaluation

using techniques like latent class analysis. The fundamental benefits of include Bayesian modeling in the methodological arsenal utilized by applied researchers are brought to light by Levy clear and thought-provoking exposition of the conceptual and practical features of Bayesian modelling, in the domains of education and educational psychology, by carefully selecting and employing research methodologies, can investigate a broader range of themes.

3. Academic Engagement

The emotional, cognitive, and behavioral aspects of student academic involvement are all seen as beneficial to their language learning. Learner commitment is measured by how emotionally invested and dedicated they are to finishing a task. One is intellectually engaged if they are both mentally challenged and wholly engrossed in the task at hand.

Significant paces toward incorporating student voice into all aspects of second language instruction. Recent Foundational Publications by SLA Researchers is one such work. In order for language learners to acquire the skills necessary to interact effectively in a target language, they must first be prepared to put in the time and effort required to practice those skills in authentic contexts. For the sake of acquiring useful linguistic skills for actual communication, this is essential. In order to help more students succeed in the long run, many professionals in the field of language education believe it is crucial to stress the importance of student agency to second-language learners.

The behavioral, emotional, and cognitive elements of language learner engagement in the language learning context were measured by survey instruments developed and piloted. The study authors have high hopes that their findings will pave the way for even more studies to be conducted in this area. To be sure, educational research has been around for a lot longer than the study of language acquisition has, so it important to keep that in mind. For instance, only recently has study began into L2 engagement in connection to learning several languages in a wide range of circumstances and cultures.

4. Conclusions

Teaching a language is an emotionally charged endeavor, requiring teachers to interact and communicate with each student as they impart the subject matter with enthusiasm in a comfortable setting. This goes beyond simply passing on content and pedagogical knowledge and using all the latest teaching methods and techniques. Only by taking these steps will this goal be reached. Therefore, the current research may be useful for those who educate and train

language teachers because it will allow them to incorporate positive psychology and its positive components into their programs, workshops, and courses for the pre-service and in-service language educators. The study of positive psychology, its key tenets, its prevalence in second language learning and teaching, and the possible teacher or student positive characteristics leading to acceptable academic outcomes, can enrich the theoretical and practical understanding of preservice teachers. Programs that prepare educators address these concerns.

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